

Role of Financial Risk Tolerance as a Mediator among Gender, Marital Status and Financial Behaviour

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The study was designed to determine whether financial risk tolerance mediates the association between gender, marital status and financial management behaviour of urban and rural area residents. A questionnaire was used to collect data from urban and rural residents of Ludhiana district ($N=400$). Socio-demographic variables such as age, education, gender, marital status and annual income were covered along with financial risk tolerance and financial behaviour. The mediation test was carried on according to the guidelines given by Zhao et al. (2010). In urban area risk tolerance was fully mediated between gender and financial behaviour and partially mediated between marital status and financial behaviour. In rural areas, no mediation of financial risk tolerance was observed between gender, marital status and financial behaviour. The need for financial education was felt to spread awareness among rural residents. So, the financial behaviour of rural residents can be improved. These findings are useful for literature that investigates behavioural finance by using pragmatic evidence from India.

Keywords: Financial risk tolerance, financial risk management, gender, marital status, mediation

In a lifetime, personal basic goals of individuals are generally savings for children education, meeting day to day expenses, travelling abroad or domestically, saving for retirement, health insurance for self and dependents and many more. Apart from this, there are financial goals such as expansion, growth and diversification of business. Some goals can be fulfilled in a short span of time, while some goals take 2-3 years or more than that. The time horizon of every goal varies. The financial management play an important role here. Financial management involves gathering background information such as records of income and expenditure (Antonides et al., 2011; Antony & Joseph, 2017). Saving, disposing off income, planning and financing through proper budgeting is known as financial management behaviour (Pandey, 2017). Managing oneself financially brings in stability and standard of living in life. The uncertain situation is where the possible outcomes are not known. Researchers mention uncertainty and risk as two different terms (Toma et al., 2012). Financial decisions are made to control identified risk. In financial management, the concept of prudence is widely followed, which says that it anticipates no profits but provides for all losses. Managing own finances is very important for everyone, from housemakers to businessmen, private salaried individuals to government employees. An individual must keep proper track of income, expenses, debt and savings (Grable & Lytton, 2001). Financial goals and time frames to complete the goals vary from person to person. Written records of financial transactions need to be made. Goals and time frame to complete the goals such as

education of children, their marriage, parents' health fund, own retirement plan fund and travelling plans, etc. need to be identified and savings need to be made accordingly. Financially literate person is one who makes informed decisions at right time (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2011). An individual's potential to invest in an event when there is possibility of risk (Grable, 2001; March & Shapira, 1987; Viadiu et al., 2006; Nobre & Grable, 2015). Often, financial risk tolerance is termed as opposite of financial risk aversion (Roszkowski & Davey, 2010; Ryack & Sheikh, 2016). According to Campbell (2006), risk tolerance involves deciding quantum of debt a person can bear, finding best financing option available, allocating income to various fixed and variable expenditures, and savings. Thus, financial risk tolerance forms inherent part of financial management and is an important study with huge scope. A person has high or low risk tolerance according to their biopsychosocial and environmental factors (Grable & Joo, 2004). Biopsychosocial factors are deeply rooted in an individual's personality and cannot be changed (Payne et al., 2019). Examples of these factors are age, gender, ethnic background and birth order. On the other hand, environmental factors are the factors which can vary from time to time such as income, education and marital status (Grable & Joo, 2004).

The literature is filled with studies of cross-cultural comparison of financial risk tolerance within countries (Nobre et al., 2016; Weber & Hsee, 1999). A few studies have focused on comparison of urban and rural populations for instance Heenkenda (2014). The paucity of knowledge about comparison of rural and urban areas in India motivates the study. The study was conducted in the pioneer smart city Ludhiana of Punjab region of India. The study of mediation is important to find out the cause and effect of variables. Determining how financial risk tolerance mediates the relation between gender, marital status and financial management behaviour of urban and rural areas can bring out the useful comparisons.

In the second section, the paper provides literature review, in third section methodology used in the paper is provided and in fourth section paper provides results and discussion and lastly, in the fifth section conclusion is provided.

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Review of Literature

Gender

Time has changed role of both men and women and also, their risk tolerance (Bajtelsmit & Bernasek, 1996). Financial awareness, educational levels and diversity of occupation vary from individual to individual. Men and women differ in goals, values and experiences (Dwyer et al., 2002). These developments significantly affect financial decision-making process at household levels (Yusof, 2015; Lee & Beatty, 2002; Malone et al., 2010; Yilmazer & Lyons, 2010). Heo et al. (2021) and Hallahan et al. (2004) mention that women are more risk-averse comparative to men as they have less financial knowledge, on the other hand, men tend to be more financially updated and are confident enough to take risk. Men are more likely to show keen interest in stock markets and also, timely filing income tax return whereas, women are more likely to show apathetic attitude. Researchers such as Miller and Stark (2002), Sapienza et al. (2009), Ardehali et al. (2005), and Grable and Roszkowski (2007) pointed out that biological difference between men and women also changed their financial psychology. Women socialise less due to family responsibility was also highlighted as a reason for gender disparity (Olsen & Cox, 2001; Yao & Hanna, 2005; Collet & Lizardo, 2009). Also, men got better opportunities to earn and females gave more priority to doing household chores (Karakowsky & Elangovan, 2001; Eckel & Grossman, 2002; Roszkowski & Grable, 2005a). All these reasons were highlighted for men to have more equity investments than women. Yusof (2015) pointed out that income also as an important reason for disparity. Another reason for gender gap cited by Dohman and Falk (2011) is that women preferred secured jobs with fixed pay and hence were risk-averse, whereas men preferred vice-versa choices. Differences in the parenting of both men and women have also been cited as a reason by the scholars to consider gender as a classifying criterion. Global Findex report 2017 showed that 56% of women were unbanked compared to 44% of men (Anonymous, 2017). Johnson and Sherraden (2007), Koitkoff and Bernheim (2000), and National Endowment for Financial Education (2004) pointed out that possessing a bank account positively influences financial behavior. This can be another reason for women to have less risk tolerance. These all can be reason for gender biased stereotypical preferences that females shy away from taking interest in investing and lose their opportunities to earn wealth (Beckmann & Menkhoff, 2008; Dwyer et al., 2002; Roszkowski & Grable, 2005a, 2005b).

Marital Status

Marital status affects an individual's risk tolerance (Lazzarone, 1996; Hallahan et al., 2004). Single individuals have less dependents on them. Hence, researchers such as Grable (2016) and Yao and Hanna (2005) mention that personal goals are priority for singletons than married ones. They live more carefree life. Married individuals have responsibilities to support dependents such as children and parents (Yao & Hanna, 2005). Financial crisis could be reason to lose status and respect in eyes of peers, colleagues, and relatives. Knowing the right risk tolerance score can mitigate financial crisis. Contrary to perceived notion researchers such as Chang et al. (2004), Hirschl et al. (2003), and Grable et al. (2009) concluded that married individuals are more risk tolerant than single, widower and divorced individuals as they have benefit of a combined income if both are earning. Income gets diversified in case of working spouse. Waite

and Gallagher (2001), McNeil (1998) alluded that marriage leads to accumulation of wealth due to better division of resources, jobs and household security.

Financial Risk Tolerance as a Possible Mediator

Owusu et al. (2023) found that financial risk tolerance acted as a mediator between financial threat, trust and financial behaviour. Hemrajani and Sharma (2017) found partial mediation of financial risk tolerance between risk and financial behaviour. Kasoga (2021) found out positive mediation of financial risk tolerance between overconfidence, availability, anchoring, representative heuristics and investment behaviour. Heo et al. (2016b) found out financial risk tolerance significantly mediates between gender and investment behaviour, and non-significantly mediates between marital status and investment behaviour. Heo et al. (2016a) found out association between gender-marital status and investment behaviour in recession years from 2008-11. The study found financial risk tolerance to be a significant mediator. Single females were found to be the most vulnerable group with lowest risk tolerance and having the least hold on investment assets. The current study aims to add to the literature by finding out how urban and rural area residents are distinct from each other.

Method

Participants

Data for the study was collected from march 2022 to September 2023 from rural and urban areas of Ludhiana district of Punjab. The sample size comprised 200 residents from each area. Total respondents in the survey were 400. The focus was laid to collect data from the breadwinner of the house. One person per family was asked to respond.

Measure

The questionnaire had 3 parts. Part 1 comprised of demographic variables such as education, age, marital status, and annual income. It is to be noted that information related to gender and marital status was only used in the analysis part of the study. For gender males were coded as 1 and females = 0; for marital status: 1= married and 0 = single. Other information about age, education and annual income was not used in the analysis.

Part 2 of the questionnaire had questions about financial risk tolerance. Grable and Lytton's (1999) financial risk tolerance scale was adapted to fit to Indian context. The summated scores of financial risk tolerance scale represent financial risk tolerance of the respondent based on criteria developed by Grable and Lytton. The financial risk tolerance scores ranged from 13 to 39, 13 being the lowest risk tolerance and 39 being highest risk tolerance. Part 3 had questions related to financial management behaviour scale. Financial behaviour was measured using 15-item scale designed by Dew and Xiao in 2011. The questionnaire was also converted into Punjabi language for convenience of residents. Cronbach's Alpha was used to find reliability of variables. The results revealed that the financial risk tolerance scale with the thirteen items had $\alpha = 0.650$ for urban area and $\alpha = 0.738$ for rural area. Financial management behaviour scale had 15 items with $\alpha = 0.787$ for urban area and $\alpha = 0.687$ for rural area.

Statistical Analysis

The analysis was carried on in IBM AMOS (Analysis of Moment

Structures) version 22. Separate analysis was conducted for urban and rural areas. Following the guidelines of Zhao et al. (2010) mediation was carried on and shown in the results section.

Procedure

Mackinnon et al. (2007) mentioned that mediation explain the mechanism by which one variable brings change in another variable. Mediation analysis assumes sequence of relationships in which an antecedent variable affects a mediating variable, which in turn affects a dependent variable.

The following illustration shows direct, indirect and total paths.

Mediator (M) = financial risk tolerance score

Independent variable (X) = socio-econ-demographic variables such as age, education etc.

Dependent variable (Y) = financial management behaviour

Flow chart (A) is also referred to as a simple cause-effect relationship and flow chart (B) as a general mediation model.

Total effect (c) refers to the overall effect of independent variable on the dependent variable.

Direct effect (c') refers to the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable in the presence of mediating variable in the model.

Indirect effect (a x b) refers to the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable through the mediator variable. Also, Indirect effect (a X b) = total effect (c) - direct effect (c')

It is important to note that the Zhao et al. (2010) highlighted that if relation between X and Y (Path c) variable is negative, mediation test should be carried on. Only if, past studies or theories mention that there is a significant relation.

Results

Table 1 showed the sample characteristics. The sample consist of 200 urban and 200 rural respondents. The data was skewed towards males. 68.5% and 85% of urban and rural respondents respectively were males. females accounted for 31.5% of urban areas and 15% of rural areas. In urban areas, 13% of respondents fall within the age group of 18-25 years, 51% of the respondents fall in the age group of 26-45 years and 34% of the respondents fall in the age group of 46-65 years. The remaining 2% were super senior citizens falling in the age group of 66 years and above. In rural areas, 11.5% of the population was in age group of 18-25 years, 51.5% of rural respondents were in age group of 26-45 years and 29.5% of the respondents fall in the age group of 46-55 years, 5% lie in age group 56-65 years and remaining 2.5% fall in retirement age of 66 years and above.

Table 2
Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Area →		Urban (N=200)		Rural (N=200)	
		Frequency	(%)	Frequency	(%)
Gender	Female	63	31.5	30	15
	Male	137	68.5	170	85
Age	18-25	26	13	23	11.5
	26-35	63	31.5	59	29.5
	36-45	39	19.5	44	22
	46-55	46	23	59	29.5
	56-65	22	11	10	5
	66 and above	4	2	5	2.5
Education	matriculation	7	3.5	27	13.5
	12th class	22	11	29	14.5
	Graduation	72	36	70	35
	Post-Graduation	99	49.5	74	37
Annual Income	Less than ₹5,00,000	34	17	42	21
	₹5,00,000 to ₹7,50,000	50	25	58	29
	₹7,50,000 to ₹10,00,000	33	16.5	37	18.5
	₹10,00,000 to ₹12,50,000	41	20.5	40	20
	₹12,50,000 to ₹15,00,000	7	3.5	10	5
Marital Status	Above ₹15,00,000	35	17.5	13	6.5
	Single	78	39	74	37
	Married	122	61	126	63

Table 1 also shows that educational attainment of the respondents ranged from matriculation to post-graduation. In urban areas, 3.5%

of the respondents had completed their matriculation, 11% of the rural respondents had passed 12th class, 36% of urban respondents

had passed graduation, and 49.5% of respondents were post-graduates. In rural areas, 13.5% of the respondents were matriculates, 14.5% of respondents were 12th pass, 35% of respondents were graduates, while remaining 37% of the respondents were post-graduates.

According to Table 1 from urban and rural areas, 17% and 21% respectively fall in income bracket of less than ₹5,00,000; 25% of urban and 29% of rural respondents had income between ₹5,00,000 to ₹7,50,000. 37 % from urban areas and 38% from rural areas had annual income ranging from ₹7,50,000 to ₹12,50,000. Further, 3.5% of urban and 5% of rural residents form part of income bracket of ₹12,50,000 to ₹15,00,000. Thereafter, 17.5% and 6.5% of urban and rural residents respectively had annual income above ₹15,00,000. Lastly, urban and rural singles accounted for 39% and 37% respectively and married individuals were 61% and 63% in urban and rural areas respectively.

Mediation of Financial Risk Tolerance between Gender and Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Area

Figure 1 and 2 shows graphical presentation of estimates of total effect, direct effect and indirect effect of gender on financial management behaviour.

Figure 1

Total Effect of Gender on Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Areas

Figure 2

Direct Effect and Indirect Effect of Gender on Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Areas

Table 2 shows the path analysis of total, direct and indirect effects of gender on financial management behaviour and financial risk tolerance playing as a mediator.

Table 2

Mediation Results of Financial Risk Tolerance between Gender and Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Area

Effect	Constructs	Unstandardized Estimation	p	Result
Total effect	Gender → FMBS (path c)	0.172	0.104	Non-Significant
Direct effect	Gender → FMBS (path c')	0.111	0.296	Non-significant
Indirect effect	Gender → FRT Score (path a)	2.32	0.001	Significant
	FRT Score → FMBS (path b)	0.026	0.009	Significant
Mediation result	Full mediation (indirect only)			

As seen in Table 2 and Figures 1 and 2, there is a non-significant total effect of gender on financial behaviour ($b = 0.172, p = 0.104$). The results revealed a significant indirect effect of gender on financial management behaviour both [a ($b = 2.32, p = 0.001$), b ($b = 0.026, p = 0.009$) paths are significant & positive as p is less than 0.05). This signifies that urban males (coded as 1) had higher risk tolerance than urban females and were more likely to have better financial management behaviour. Direct effect is non-significant ($b = 0.111, p = 0.296 > 0.05$) which means that when mediator is constant, gender does not show impact on financial behaviour. According to Zhao et al. (2010), the results indicate that there is full mediation of financial risk tolerance on the relationship between gender and financial management behaviour.

$$VAF \text{ (Variance Accounted For)} = \text{Indirect effect} / \text{Total effect} = (2.32 * 0.026) / 0.172 = 0.0632 / 0.172 = 0.37$$

VAF (%) = 37%. This indicates that strength of mediation is moderate.

Mediation of Financial Risk Tolerance between Gender and Financial Management Behaviour in Rural Areas

The following Figures 3 and 4 shows graphical presentation of coefficient estimates of mediation paths of gender on financial

management behaviour in rural areas.

Figure 3

Total Effect of Gender on Financial Management Behaviour in Rural Areas

Figure 4

Direct Effect and Indirect Effect of Gender on Financial Management Behaviour in Rural Areas

Table 3 show the path analysis of total, direct and indirect effect of gender on financial management behaviour and mediator financial risk tolerance.

Table 3

Mediation Results of Financial Risk Tolerance of Gender on Financial Management Behaviour

Effect	Constructs	Standardized Estimation	p	Result
Total effect	Gender → FMBS (path c)	0.224	0.077	Non-Significant
Direct effect	Gender → FMBS (path c')	0.22	0.080	Non-significant
Indirect effect	Gender → FRT Score (path a)	1.18	0.835	Non-Significant
	FRT Score → FMBS (path b)	0.002	0.002	Significant
Mediation result	no effect non-mediation			

As seen in Table 3 and Figures 3 and 4, there is a non-significant total effect ($b = 0.224, p = 0.077$) of gender on financial behaviour. The results were insignificant at 0.05 level. Moreover, the results revealed a non-significant indirect effect [a path ($b = 1.18, p = 0.835$), b path ($b = 0.0026, p = 0.002$)] of gender on financial management behaviour. Since both direct ($b = 0.22, p = 0.08$), and indirect effect are also insignificant no effect non-mediation exists in rural area. The result implies that financial risk tolerance does not mediate between gender and financial management behaviour.

Mediation of Financial Risk Tolerance between Marital Status and Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Areas

After studying mediation of financial risk tolerance between gender and financial management behaviour further, analysis was conducted to check relation between marital status and financial management behaviour. Figures 5 and 6 shows graphical presentation of results in urban areas.

Figure 5

Total Effect of Marital Status on Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Areas

Figure 6

Direct Effect and Indirect Effect of Marital Status on Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Areas

Table 4 and Figures 5 and 6 shows path analysis of total, direct and indirect effect of marital status on financial management behaviour in urban areas and financial risk tolerance playing a mediating role.

Table 4

Mediation Results of Financial Risk Tolerance between Marital Status and Financial Management Behaviour in Urban Areas

Effect	Constructs	Standardized Estimation	p	Result
Total effect	Marital status → FMBS (path c)	0.21	0.037	Significant
Direct effect	Marital status → FMBS (path c')	0.254	0.010	Significant
Indirect effect	Marital status → FRT Score (path a)	-1.394	0.048	Significant
	FRT Score → FMBS (path b)	0.032	0.001	Significant
Mediation result	Competitive partial mediation			

It can be seen in Table 4 that total impact of marital status on financial behaviour ($b = 0.21, p = 0.037$) was significant at 0.05 level. Married individuals (coded as 1) showed better financial behaviour overall. Also, the results revealed a significant indirect effect of impact of marital status on financial management behaviour [both a ($b = -1.40, p = 0.048$), b ($b = 0.032, p = 0.001$) paths are significant]. It is to be noted that association between marital status and financial risk tolerance was significant but negative. Urban married individuals exhibited lower levels of

tolerance for financial risk compared with single individuals. Path a and b showed that married urban individuals had lower financial management behaviour by reducing their financial risk tolerance. But direct effect is significant and positive ($b = 0.541, p = 0.010$). Competitive partial mediation exists as mediated effect (a x b) is negative and direct effect (c') is positive.

VAF = 0.21; VAF (%) = 21%. This indicates that mediation has moderate strength.

Mediation of Financial Risk Tolerance between Marital Status and Financial Management Behaviour in Rural Areas

The following Figures 7 and 8 show graphical presentation of mediation analysis in rural areas.

Figure 7

Total Effect of Marital Status on Financial Management Behaviour in Rural Areas

Table 5

Mediation Results of Financial Risk Tolerance between Marital Status and Financial Management Behaviour in Rural Area

Effect	Constructs	Standardized Estimation	p	Result
Total effect	Marital status → FMBS (path c)	0.26	0.005	Significant
Direct effect	Marital status → FMBS (path c')	0.274	0.003	Significant
Indirect effect	Marital status v FRT Score (path a)	-2.124	0.012	Significant
	FRT Score → FMBS (path b)	0.007	0.399	Non-Significant
Mediation result	Direct only non-mediation			

It can be seen in Table 5 and Figures 7 and 8 that total of marital status on financial behaviour ($b = 0.26, p = 0.005$) was significant at 0.05 level. Married individuals in rural area had better financial management behaviour than singles. Path a was also significant but negative ($b = -2.124, p = 0.012$). This indicates that married individuals in rural area show lower financial risk tolerance than single ones. But path b was not significant indicating no association between risk tolerance scores and financial behaviour ($b = 0.007, p = 0.399$). Direct effect was significant ($b = 0.274, p = 0.003$). According to guidelines given by Zhao et al. (2010), if indirect effect is non-significant but direct effect is significant direct only non-mediation exists. Therefore, in rural areas, financial risk tolerance does not mediate between marital status and financial behaviour.

Discussion

Total effect of gender on financial behaviour in both urban and rural areas was non-significant which contrast to studies such as Andreeva and Matuszyk (2019), Berggren and Romualdo (2010), Walczak and Pieńkowska-Kamieniecka (2018). These studies show indirect gendered management behaviour. Results in Table 2 shows indirect only mediation between gender and financial management behaviour in urban areas. Gender influence financial management behaviour only through specific channel of financial risk tolerance. In contrast, the rural settlements in Table 3 showed no significant direct, indirect or total effects. This indicates constraints of rural life-such as limited financial products or rigid communal norms fails mediation.

Agunsoye et al. (2022), Copur and Eker (2014), Godwin and Carroll (1986) found significant relation of marital status on financial management behaviour. As shown in Table 4 and 5 across

Figure 8

Direct Effect and Indirect Effect of Marital Status on Financial Management Behaviour in Rural Areas

The study assessed the mediating role of financial risk tolerance on the relationship between marital status and financial management behaviour in rural areas. Table 5 shows the summary of results:

both regions, the transition to marriage significantly reduces financial risk tolerance suggesting a protective behaviour upon entering marriage. In urban areas, there are more financial choices, marriage reduces risk appetite which successfully translates into management behaviour (significant path b). In rural settlements, married individuals become more cautious in spirit. Also, there is lack of diverse financial instruments and the weight of traditional household roles force standardized financial management behaviour that remains indifferent to personal risk preferences.

The study advises policymakers that in urban areas financial education need to be given to help people understand their risk tolerance so that they can manage money. In rural areas policy makers should lay focus on both education and infrastructure. So that rural people can get better access to banks and understand digital tools and make better choices. It is important to note that in rural areas changing mindset through education alone won't help until they have better tools and more financial choices.

The study uses the self-reported data which is prone to limitations as participants may have provided socially desirable answers. Also, study uses cross-sectional data. Future studies are suggested to use longitudinal data to provide better cause and effect. Future studies can also focus more on rural areas and add to literature by capturing hidden differences between a farming village and a rural trading town.

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